

PLANNING THE LESSON PROCESS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: Proper, effective and meaningful organization and planning of foreign language lessons is one of the urgent issues today. Because the lesson planning process depends not only on the knowledge and experience of the teacher, but also on several external factors that should be paid special attention. These factors include the language teaching criteria to be applied to the lesson, the standards to be met, and the curriculum. Therefore, the question arises that if we follow what we can plan the lesson of a foreign language correctly.

Key words: Planning, lesson, process, teaching, foreign languages

It is known that in every country there are certain ideas about the goals that the teacher sets for himself in the teaching of foreign languages, the ways to achieve them and the methods of checking the level of achievement. From this point of view, in the last ten years, in many countries, a new approach to language learning was formed based on didactic-methodical principles. The main document in this regard is the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR).

The system of pan-European competences of language knowledge, i.e. CEFR, was introduced in 2001, which contains special standards of foreign language skills and evaluation criteria. Currently, CEFR is accepted as a basic system for determining the level of foreign language knowledge and forming the curriculum in many countries of the world, including in our country, starting from 2013, from the initial stage of school education, DTS (State Education Standard)

educational textbooks published based on the requirements of the system of pan-European competences of language knowledge were developed in the section of topics from level A1 to level B2 and introduced into education.

In this, the definition of "to be able to do" as a goal set in the process of language teaching and learning is leading, that is, the goal set by the teacher for each lesson is that the student should be able to do it after this lesson. or not the skills they need to learn, but rather the knowledge they can achieve and the skills they can apply in practice, and plans the lesson accordingly. As a result,

during the lesson, the language learner learns to communicate with each other in various situations and life processes, to express his personal opinion freely, and to enter into dialogue by evaluating the worldview and mentality of representatives of other nations and cultures. In this process, based on communicative language competence, it is envisaged to gradually develop students' communication skills by creating live communication conditions based on the production and/or reception of texts related to various aspects of life. In this regard, in order for the teacher to correctly understand the goal he is setting for himself, first of all, we need to correctly understand the meaning of the word competence..

Competence - It is the ability to use the theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications acquired in science to solve the practical and theoretical problems encountered in everyday life and apply them in practice. [1]

Competencies - it is a combination of declarative knowledge, procedural skills, and personality-related competencies that enable an individual to perform actions.[2;19]

Declarative Knowledge:

- real knowledge, a complex of knowledge based on facts (for example, knowledge of grammatical rules or a correct understanding and understanding of a specific characteristic of a certain culture, society;

Procedural (available, acquired) skills refer to both low and high automated skills. For example, the automatic application of language rules and norms of a particular society;

Personal competence is a sum of individual characteristics, personality traits and attitudes. These include, for example, attitudes towards the target culture, motivation to learn the language, and stable personality factors such as more or less underachievement or self-confidence.

Based on the table below, we can consider the situations in which the above-mentioned qualifications and skills are used in the process of language learning:

T/r	Process	Appropriate qualification type
1.	expressing sympathy in communication	personal qualification
2.	to be able to correctly use forms of greeting in German	declarative knowledge
3.	distinguish letters quickly and easily	procedural (existing, acquired) skills

4.	to be able to correctly list the modal verbs in the German language	declarative knowledge
5.	the ability to receive information when a representative of a certain language speaks very quickly	personal qualification
6.	being able to pronounce the letter "r" correctly in German	procedural (existing, acquired) skills

In order to provide students with competence-oriented knowledge, the teacher must first get used to looking at the educational material to be learned from the student's point of view. The educational materials provided by the teacher should be prepared gradually from simple to complex and should include words and phrases that are frequently used during each lesson and in everyday life. Sometimes it is more effective to provide additional materials that deviate from the teaching materials provided in the textbooks. For example, telenovelas such as "Jojo sucht das Glück", "Nikos Weg", "Mein Weg nach Deutschland", offered by the Deutsche Welle platform and the Goethe Institute for German language learners, are suitable for young people's lives, are adapted to different language levels, and deal with everyday life problems. is distinguished by its dependence. Also, the role of project lessons in developing students' communicative competence is incomparable. In this case, the teacher brings the students to a new environment by organizing the lessons outside the school environment, say, in a museum, on the street, in the heart of nature. z can prepare presentations and acquire language in an action-oriented manner.

In conclusion, the teacher should pay special attention to the following aspects when planning foreign language lessons:

- To be able to correctly present the educational material in the lesson and deliver it to the students, so that at the end of the lesson, the student can return the learned material, that is, he can use it in the lesson and in everyday life;
- The knowledge learned by the student should be demonstrated and evaluated in the form of written and oral speech;
- The presented materials should be based on listening, i.e. through the ears, or seeing, i.e. through the eyes.

Also, it is appropriate for the teacher to pay attention to the following when creating a communicative environment in the lesson:

1. Do not translate the instructions for the students in the lesson, that is, let the student try to understand what is said on his own.

2. In class, students should not always sit in the same seat with the same classmate, but on the contrary, they should communicate with different classmates during different group work.
3. It is appropriate to patiently ask all students, not just one student.
4. When explaining a new topic, it is not necessary to comment on previously familiar things. Because our task is to think together with the student, not for the student.
5. During group work, entrust the group with the help of an answer sheet to check the result, limit individual control a little.

In general, when planning the lesson, the teacher should take into account the specific knowledge that the students will learn after this lesson. For this, it is required from the teacher to be creative, to abandon homogeneity in the lesson and to activate the ability to make the student interested in science.

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